

Towards Responsible AI: Explainable AI as a Catalyst for Participatory Development Practices

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This paper builds on the call for more human-centred XAI (explainable AI), arguing that XAI is a necessary but under-researched component of meaningful participatory AI. To enable the meaningful participation of diverse stakeholder communities at various points in the AI lifecycle, they must be able to understand, interpret, and scrutinise the entire socio-technical system. However, while significant research has centred on XAI, much of this has been primarily useful for developers, those with expert knowledge, or specific end-users. XAI solutions tailored to affected or other interested communities are currently less explored – especially how information needs change along the AI lifecycle. This paper sets out to stimulate discussion on how XAI can support the meaningful involvement of affected and other communities—an essential step towards more responsible AI systems—by highlighting current challenges and proposing a research agenda for moving forward.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Participatory AI, Development, Responsible AI, Stakeholder Engagement, Explainable AI, Transparency, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170408

1 Introduction

Moving towards more responsible AI development practices is a pressing concern, partly driven by numerous incidents where AI systems have resulted in negative impacts [30]. *Explainable AI* (XAI) is often considered key aspect of responsible AI, i.e. where AI systems provide information to render themselves less opaque and more human-comprehensible. XAI can focus on different aspects of the system, e.g. a model’s general operation or why a specific recommendation/output was provided [11]. XAI has been a topic of research for several years, but in practice, much of the work has primarily served those with technical expertise; e.g. developers seeking to debug systems or to conduct technical audits [4, 14, 37]. Whilst important, supporting transparency for all communities that may be affected by or have an interest in the system appears less-considered – despite this being (directly/indirectly) encouraged by guidance documents [15, 16, 31–35] and regulations [41]. Thus, a shift towards more human-centred (vs. only developer- or user-centred) XAI is an essential step towards more responsible AI development, and various works are calling for and inducing such shift [e.g. 3, 7, 12, 14, 19, 28, 38–41].

This work endorses this shift of the audience of XAI. Importantly, we want to emphasise that **inclusive XAI has an essential role for meaningful participatory AI development**. *Participatory AI* (also termed *stakeholder involvement (ShI)*) refers to the process of engaging affected communities and other groups with a stake in the system throughout the AI lifecycle in order to understand their needs and concerns regarding the system’s application context and to ensure these are considered during the system’s design [8, 9, 20]. Such participatory approaches have been associated with benefits such as (i) a better understanding of the system’s socio-technical context [6, 25, 26, 44] and thus (ii) the improved detection (and thus mitigation) of potential risks and harms [10, 26, 43], as well as (iii) a shift of decision power during development towards the communities the system will affect [5, 8, 20, 38, 42]. However, to harness these benefits along the entire AI lifecycle—including during system development and testing—all affected communities

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(including non-users) and those with an interest in the system have to be able to scrutinise and understand the system and its context so that they can provide informed opinions and recommend adjustments. Thus, XAI that is appropriately tailored and accessible to the diverse stakeholders of a system is key to unlocking meaningful engagement – beyond early explorations of needs in an application context [7, 19, 38].

2 Background: Various Stakeholder Communities are Insufficiently Involved During Model Development and Testing

In previous works [e.g. 20–22, 36], we investigated stakeholder involvement practices along the AI lifecycle (see [2] for details on lifecycle stages). We found that the majority of literature, guidance, and tooling for participatory AI development focused on early explorations (i.e. objective setting stage and system requirements definition stage) where communities are involved to explore their broad needs, wishes, and concerns in the system’s application context. However, involvements at later stages—for instance, when a system’s model and test results become more concrete—has largely been overlooked in research on stakeholder involvement. For example, in a study in which we analysed existing tools that support AI practitioners’ stakeholder involvement efforts, we found only a single tool that supports community engagement during the testing stage [21]. This lack of attention for stakeholder involvement at later stages of the lifecycle is detrimental: it prevents not only continuous stakeholder involvement along the AI lifecycle (which is essential, see [20, 22]), but also renders system assessments that go beyond technical performance tests as difficult or impossible. As a result, the accountability towards involved stakeholders is diminished [8, 20]. We want to emphasise that this is especially important in a time of growing calls for participatory AI development that advances rAI efforts [e.g. 5, 8, 9, 17, 18, 20–22, 26, 27, 36], which is not yet sufficiently supported throughout the AI lifecycle in practice.

While the lack of stakeholder involvement at the development and testing stages is a general issue of participatory AI development (i.e. not something that is XAI-specific), we suspect similar issues during stakeholder involvement for the development of human-centred XAI methods. However, we also believe that **XAI has the potential to significantly improve participatory AI development**, by providing a mechanism for unlocking more meaningful stakeholder involvement along the entire AI lifecycle (as we next explore).

3 XAI as Key to Unlock More Inclusive Participatory AI Development Practices

We see a real opportunity for XAI to enable greater stakeholder involvement, particularly during system development and testing. A key barrier to broader engagement at these stages may be the perception that AI systems are too complex to explain in ways that allow for meaningful participation or useful input from affected and interested communities. **Tailored, inclusive, and more human-centred XAI methods could help to overcome these barriers**, i.e. by providing stakeholders with the insights required in a manner that helps them understand, scrutinise, and evaluate whether the system fits their needs [1, 7, 12, 19, 38]. For example, Cobbe et al. [7] highlight that information about a system supports its reviewability (i.e. its understanding and scrutiny) only if it is *contextually appropriate*; that is, if the information provided, the way it is presented, and the form it takes all are all aligned with the audience’s needs and goals for making sense of, evaluating, or acting upon that information (thereby supporting accountability).

How audience-appropriate information can unlock the involvement of stakeholders with low levels of (AI) literacy has been illustrated in a study by Kuo et al. [24]: they involve civil servants and unhoused individuals through comicboarding to assess their needs and preferences regarding an algorithmic decision-support tool that supports emergency housing allocation. Such methods show promise in making XAI more accessible to a broader audience – for example, by visually representing explanation techniques (such as feature importance, confidence levels, or example-based explanations),

and by clarifying when and how a particular explanation method is appropriate or useful within a given context. In this manner, all stakeholders (especially and importantly including affected communities) would be able to scrutinise the model's (and systems) operations, including before it is deployed, flagging inaccuracies, risks, and harms so they can be handled. In short, more continuous and inclusive/accessible stakeholder involvement beyond early deliberations would further align AI development practices with responsible AI efforts.

However, XAI that is tailored to different stakeholders and to their information needs at different phases of the lifecycle is currently under-researched. Thus, we urge the CHI and related communities to explore **how the relevant stakeholder groups and their information needs differ along the AI lifecycle**, so to support meaningful engagement. In previous studies, we emphasise the need for contextually appropriate information to supporting meaningful transparency during system development; arguing the case generally [7], as well in particular contexts such as for clinicians (here varying with their level of familiarity with the system) [40]. Both studies emphasise not only that user needs are dynamic, but also that different stakeholders prioritise insights at different stages of the AI lifecycle [13]. Importantly, these stakeholder needs can vary based on multiple factors, including the community's level of expertise, prior experience with AI systems, the domain or use case, and perceptions of the trustworthiness of the developing organisation – factors that several studies have shown to significantly influence information expectations [e.g. 3, 7, 19, 23, 29]. These findings further emphasise that different XAI methods and approaches might be needed at different stages of the AI lifecycle, driven by the specific information requirements of the various stakeholders. However, we currently lack insights into the methods, practices, and design considerations best suited to meeting these needs in context. This lack of knowledge hinders XAI that is tailored to specific stakeholder needs, limiting its potential to provide information that effectively supports more continuous and meaningful stakeholder involvement (as well as accountability more generally). To help address these aspects, the next section outlines a research agenda focused on better understanding and supporting these diverse requirements.

4 Open Questions & Preliminary Research Agenda

We suggest following research agenda as a starting point to explore the type of XAI that is required to support more continuous and inclusive participatory AI development. It is designed to stimulate discussions and research that addresses current areas of uncertainty, i.e. how we can better use XAI to unlock more inclusive AI development practices and thus more responsible AI systems.

4.1 Understanding XAI needs across AI lifecycle stages

- (1) **Information needs along the lifecycle.** How do the information needs of involved communities change as system development progresses through the AI lifecycle?
- (2) **Purpose of XAI.** What is the purpose and benefit of XAI for each stage of the AI lifecycle?
- (3) **Relevant Factors.** What are the factors that influence information needs? These might include exploring:
 - (a) Level of expertise of the involved community, technical as well as in the lived experience.
 - (b) Role of the involved community, e.g. clinician, hospital IT expert, patient (see 4.2, point (2))
 - (c) Use case of the system, i.e. the system's objective.
 - (d) Perceived trustworthiness of the system creator (team or organisation).
 - (e) Involvement strategies, i.e. whether communities were involved from the outset.
 - (f) Which other factors are important here?

- (4) **General purpose AI.** How does this change for e.g. LLMs where use cases are vast and hard to pinpoint while stakeholders are extremely diverse?

4.2 Involved Communities during XAI development – and using XAI for AI development more broadly

- (1) **Communities in focus.** Which communities should be involved for more responsible AI development? How can we ensure that especially at-risk communities are included? This question concerns AI development more broadly, also outside of XAI efforts.
- (a) Which communities are especially relevant at which stage of the AI development lifecycle – or does this change at all? This question concerns AI development more broadly, also outside of XAI efforts.
 - (b) How can especially at-risk communities be accessed in a respectful manner, e.g. preserving their privacy and well-being?
 - (c) What are barriers beyond the typical challenges of responsible stakeholder involvement [20], i.e. challenges unique to including stakeholders with XAI methods?
- (2) **Information need per community.** What are the most crucial aspects of the system that each community has to understand? How does this change with the deployment context/industry?
- (3) **Relationship between XAI and participation.** Which interplay of XAI and participation is required to advance responsible AI efforts (instead of e.g. commercial interests)?

4.3 Implementing XAI that addresses these needs

- (1) **Type of XAI.** Considering the information needs/role of XAI at each stage of the AI lifecycle, what type of XAI is most suitable to fulfil these (e.g. model- and outcome-specific explanations)?
- (2) **Inclusive XAI.** Responsible AI development requires the participation of *all* affected communities, especially at-risk groups. How can we design XAI to make it accessible to all? We see a clear risk to design XAI that is only useful for specific, e.g. highly educated sub-groups, meaning that at-risk communities are further disadvantaged.
- (3) **Balancing detail with overload.** How can we provide sufficient details for meaningful participation while preventing information overload?
- (4) **Universality of guidance.** What is the correct balance on universal guidance on XAI for participatory development vs guidance that is tailored to a specific use case or industry?
- (5) **Practicability of guidance.** How can we make guidance more actionable as current research [see e.g. 39] shows that AI practitioners struggle to translate XAI guidance to their own projects?.

5 Summary & Moving Forward

In this paper, we have positioned XAI as an essential component in unlocking more participatory and responsible development practices throughout the process of AI development. We bring this discussion to CHI to engage the community in a timely and informed dialogue. Highlighting the role of XAI in supporting participatory approaches is critical now – so that the CHI and responsible AI communities can collaboratively identify concrete ways forward and foster future research and collaboration toward more transparent and accountable AI systems.

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